

Study of Macro-Morphology and Agricultural Implication of Soils with Iron Concretions in Eastern Kogi State of Nigeria

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Abstract: This study considered the macro-morphology and agricultural implication of soils with concretions in Kogi state of Nigeria. Iron and manganese concretions are common in soils of Nigeria, thus the need arises to look at the agricultural implication which is a key issue in food security. The study adopted a free survey method. Two pedons were studied. The colour of the soils typifies the presence of concretions in the soils. One the major agricultural implications is the release of part of the phosphorus sorbed which enhances the phosphorus content in the soils.

Keywords: Manganese, Iron, Phosphorus, Pedon, Sorption, Concretion

Introduction

The occurrence of ferruginous concretions is an important morphological feature of some soils in Nigeria. According to Pattil and Dasog (1997), if there is a periodicity in the supply of iron, concentrations with a concentric fabric result. The localized re-distribution of iron results in mottles, which with time may transform into nodules and concretions (Eswaram *et al.* 1990). Iron (Fe)-enriched concretions is a complex natural matrix with high chemical heterogeneity and phosphate-sorption capacity (Gasparatos and Haidoutic, 2006).

Iron –manganese concretions have been found to be widespread in soils with some internal drainage restrictions (Gasparatos et

al., 2004; Zhang and Karathanasis 1997). These firm to extremely firm sub-rounded discrete bodies are formed by the processes of reduction, translocation, and oxidation of Fe and Mn. During wet periods, Fe(III) and Mn(III/IV) are reduced and dispersed throughout the soil matrix, whereas during drying periods they reprecipitate, lining or filling matrix pores. Repetition of this process forms these millimeter-sized redoximorphic features with distinct concentric structures of alternating Fe- and Mn-rich zones. Therefore, Fe-Mn concretions are characterized by a greater concentration of Fe and Mn oxides than the surrounding soil matrix capacity (Gasparatos and Haidoutic, 2006).

The nature of Fe and Mn oxides in soil concretions is of great interest from the viewpoints of both pedogenesis, crop production and environmental chemistry (Gasparatos *et al.* 2005). Studies on the dynamic role of Fe oxides in the soil system have shown the need for the expansion of current knowledge on the properties and morphology of natural secondary iron oxide accumulations such as concretions (Gasparatos *et al.*, 2004; Gasparatos *et al.* 2005).

Attempt has been made to explain the genesis of iron concretions (Pattil and Dasog, 1997), however there is dearth of information on the agricultural implication of soils with concretions in Nigeria. Therefore, this research aimed at studying the macro-morphology and agricultural implication of soils with redox concentration in eastern Kogi State of Nigeria.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

The study area is situated within the eastern zone of Kogi State. Kogi State in turn is situated within the middle belt of Nigeria. Kogi State lies within latitudes 6°51'N to 7°54'N and longitudes 6°45'E to 7°38'E with elevation of above 200 m above mean sea level.

Climate of the Study Area

These two distinct seasons in the area of study are rainy season which lasts from April to October and the dry season observed between November and March. A part of the dry season is very dusty and cold as a result of the north-easterly winds that bring about the harmattan. This zone has an annual rainfall ranging from 1100 to 1300 mm with a mean of 1200 mm per annum. The average monthly temperature varies between 17 and 36°C (Ukabiala, 2022). The highest temperature (36°C) has been recorded during the dry season, while the mean relative humidity is lowest during the

dry season and highest during the rainy season of the years, giving 15 and 67% respectively (Ukabiala *et al.*, 2022).

Vegetation of the Study Area

The study area is characterized by different types of vegetation which are not in their natural luxuriant state owing to the human use of the forest and the resultant derived deciduous and savanna vegetation. Harvesting of firewood on one of the causes of deforestation in the area. These trees include Locust bean (*Ceratonia siligua*), Shea butter tree (*Vitellaria paradoxa*), Oil bean (*Phaseolus spp*) and the *Isoberlinia* trees, Iroko (*Chlorophora spp*), and Mahogany (*Khaya spp*), Venus's Flytrap (*Dionaea muscipula*), Banyan (*Ficus benghalensis*), Tumbleweed (*Amaranthus graecizans*), African whitewood – Obeche (*Triplochiton scleroxylon*), Sumac (*Rhus coriaria*), Balsam (*Impatiens pallida*), and Boxleaf myrtle (*Paxistima myrtifolia*) amongst others. Along the flood plains are also found Palms (*guineense spp*), Holly (*Ilex opaca*), Plane tree (*Platanus orientalis*), Willow (*Salix babylomica*) Some of the trees are very useful species and source of food to man. Such trees include Oil palm (*Elaeis guineensis*), Mango trees (*Mangifera indica*), Oranges (*Citrus spp*).

Physiography and Soils of the Study Area

The lands are characterized by undulating plains with slope ranging from 2 to 4 percent. The soils of the eastern Kogi are loamy and characterized to be strongly to slightly acid in reaction, low contents of organic carbon, low to very low total nitrogen, low available phosphorus and moderate to high cation exchange capacity (Akpan-Idiok *et al.*, 2013; Ukabiala, 2022). The drainage system around the study area is that of the natural slope where water flows through the drainage channel, and guided by the undulating nature of the landscape.

Field Work

Free soil survey technique was employed in the study. Soils with redox concentrations were identified within Okowowolo and Ogugu. The two (2) soil profiles used were name KE₁ (07°34'35.8"N, 006°03'30.1"E) and KE₂ (07°10'04.8"N, 007°29'11.9"E). The soil profiles are shown in plates 1 and 2. The slope of KE₁ and KE₂ ranged from 2 to 4%. The soil profiles their environs were morphologically described following USDA guidelines for description by Schoeneberger *et al.* (2012). The horizons were properly delineated while the colour of the soils from each horizon was read from the Munsell Soil Colour Chart. The soil texture was determined by hand-feel method. Other macro-morphological features that were observed include the soil structure, soil consistence, pores, roots, horizon boundaries as well as inclusions.

Results and Discussion

The KE₁ and KE₂ soil profiles showed good horizon development. Ap layers formed the epipedons while the subsurface layers are characterized by illuvial horizons of silicate clays and iron (B horizon) with definite characteristics of concretions and fragipan character (KE₁ – 35-70 and 70 -110 cm). In KE₂ soil profile, the subsoils are characterized by illuvial layers with concretions (Btc). At the depths of 50-70 cm and 70-110 cm, there was illuvial accumulation of sesquioxides. Similar horizonation was reported by Pattil and Dasog (1997).

The presence of Fe-Mn concretions dominant in the pedons is an indication of redox concentrations in the soil layers. Similar redoximorphic features occurred in a Fine, Mixed, Semiactive, Isohyperthermic Typic Haplustalfs located at Killikulam Agriculture College, India but on a lower landscape of elevation, 23 m above mean sea level (Soil Survey Staff, 1999). The agricultural implication of this could be rapid hydraulic conductivity of the soils as a

result of presence of coarse materials (concretion) that will create large diameter pores. Another implication of environmental concern is that the presence of macropores would create substantial increase in rates of movement of soluble pollutants from soils (White, 1986).

The typic hue of the soils is mainly 2.5YR in the surface with an exception of 10R at the last depth of KE₁. The description ranged from bright brown through to dark reddish brown (2.5YR2/2). The subsurface of KE₂ (50 – 110 cm) had orange matrix colour (2.5YR6/8). The colour shades typifies well drained soils. The structure of the soils was granular in the A horizons. Crumb and subangular blocky structure was observed in the B horizons. The wet consistence of the soils was dominantly non sticky and non plastic in the A horizon while the B horizons were slightly sticky and slightly plastic.

The observation of the soil horizon boundaries showed clear and smooth topography as well as abrupt and wavy topography in the A horizons. The horizon boundaries between the B horizons are gradual smooth, clear smooth and diffuse smooth. The pores observed in the surface soils were common, fine and medium in abundance and fine (1 to 2 mm) in diameter. Common and fine pores were encountered in the upper B layers while few and fine pore occurred in the lower B horizons. The roots observed in the surface soil layers were common and many in abundance, and fine in size. In the subsurface soils, the roots were mainly few in abundance and very fine in size. Medium roots are observed in the subsurface of KE₂.

The entire horizons of the soil profiles are characterized by many iron and concretions throughout the profiles. Soils with hues between red and yellow are caused by various forms and concentration of Fe (III) oxides. Pattil and Dasog (1997) reported that, in the Fe (II) form, iron is mobile and is transported to points where the

accumulation takes place through accretion. Once a nucleus is formed, the nodule grows since the nucleus serves as a template for further deposition.

Table 1: Macro-morphological properties of Kogi east soils

Pedon/ Coordinate	Location	Horizon depth (cm)	Horizon designation	Colour (Moist)		Texture	Structure	Consistence		Boundary	Pores	Roots	Others
				Matrix	Mottles			Wet	Moist				
KE ₁ 07°34'35.8"N 006°03'30.1"E	Okowowolo	0-15	Ap1	2.5YR4/3	-	gsl	15g	nsnp	l	cs	mfi	mfi	Fe-Mn concretions
		15-35	Apc	2.5YR3/6	-	gls	15c	nsnp	vfr	gs	cfi	fvfi	Fe-Mn concretions
		35-70	Btcx1	2.5YR3.7/6.5	-	vg scl	15csbk	sssp	vfr	gs	cfi	fvfi	Fe-Mn concretions
		70-110	Btcx2	10R4/8	-	egsc	25c	sssp	fr	-	ffi	fvfi	cementation
KE ₂ 07°10'04.8"N 007°29'11.9"E	Ogugu	0-12	Ap	2.5YR3/1	-	gl	15g	nsnp	l	aw	cfi	mfi	Fe-Mn concretions
		12-29	Bc	2.5YR4/6	-	gsl	25gc	nsnp	fr	cs	fme	cme	Fe-Mn concretions
		29-50	Btc	2.5YR5/6	-	vgsl	24g	nsnp	vfr	gs	cfi	cfi	Few black ants, Fe-Mn concretions
		50-70	Btcs1	2.5YR6/8	-	vg scl	245c	sssp	vfr	ds	ffi	fvfi	Fe concretions, clay skins on ped faces
		70-110	Btcs2	2.5YR6/8	-	egsc	25c	sssp	vfr	-	ffi	fvfi	Fe concretions, clay skins on ped faces

Structure: 1 = weak, 2 = moderate, 4 = fine, 5 = medium, c = crumb, g = granular, sbk= subangular

Texture: g = gravelly, v = very, e = extremely, l = loam, c = clay, sl = sandy loam, ls = loamy sand, scl = sandy clay loam, sc = sandy clay

Consistency: nsnp = non sticky and non plastic, sssp = slightly sticky and slightly plastic, l = loose, vfr = very friable, fr = friable,

Pores and Roots: f = few, m = many, c = common, fi = fine, me = medium

Boundary: a = abrupt, c = clear, g = gradual, d = diffuse, s = smooth, w = wavy

Plate 1: Soil Profile of KE₁

Plate 2: Soil Profile of KE₂

Agricultural Implications of Iron Concretions in the Soils

A common effect of iron concretions is on phosphorus availability (Abekoe, 2021). Phosphorus deficiency is widespread in most soils of Nigeria (Ukabiala, 2022; Ukabiala *et al.* 2022). Phosphorus (P) is an essential nutrient for plant growth and therefore an adequate supply of P with fertilization is a key component of increasing soil productivity and profitable agriculture (Ukabiala, 2022). Presence of lateritic concretions in some of the soils constitutes an additional limitation to crop production because the concretions act as an effective sink for added P (Abekoe, 2021). In Abekoe's assessment, a soil originally containing 70% concretions was fractionated into soil fines and concretions and the soil reconstituted to represent varying amounts of the concretions. Phosphate sorption and desorption studies were carried out on the samples. This result suggested that both concretions and soil fines have an equivalent amount of labile P pool though the rate of P release is lower in the concretions than in the soil fines. Abekoe's findings also affirmed higher P release in the concretionary soils and an earlier exhaustion of P in the soil fines. Thus, it could be postulated that concretions do release part of the phosphorus sorbed but the major difference between the concretions and soil fines is the rate of P release.

In another research, the active non-crystalline Fe and aluminium (Al) oxides (Feox, Alox), oxalate extractable P (Pox), P sorption capacity (PSC), and the degree of P saturation (DPS) of Fe-enriched concretions from agricultural imperfectly drained soils were determined using the acid ammonium oxalate method (Gasparatos and Haidoutic, 2006). The findings

revealed that concretions contain 13 times as much Feox, twice as much Alox, and almost 15 times as much Pox in the soils with concretions than the surrounding soil matrix. Pox accounted for 50–80% of total P of the soil concretions, indicating strong accumulation of non-crystalline P components (Al- and Fe-P). A research by Emmanuel (2015) on concretionary nodules as nutrients sinks revealed that concretions were shown to accumulate high concentration of the total elements analysed.

The presence of Fe-Mn concretions could influence the contents of manganese, iron, copper and Nickel of the soils in the soils of Kogi east. This is reflected by the much redder colour of the soils. Rare earths show an enrichment sequence: parent rock ---+ soil ---+ soil concretion (Glasby *et al.*, 1979).

Conclusion

The study considered the agricultural implication of soil rich in Fe-Mn concretions in eastern Kogi state of Nigeria. The findings revealed that the presence of these concretion influence some properties of soils that influence agricultural production. Such properties include the availability of phosphorus.

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